

Product-Service Systems Design for E-Waste Management: A Case Study of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre in Nairobi County

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Abstract

This paper develops a product service system for e-waste management in Nairobi County. Due to improper management system for e-waste and policies, informal recycling procedures are used which poses unpleasant health and environmental effects. Evaluation and establishment of efficient integrated e-waste management system was critical. From the case study, there were existing gaps in collection, transportation, financing, producer responsibility, consumer awareness, stakeholder collaboration and in lack of e-waste flow monitoring policies. The System developed advocates for a shift from provision of products to provision of systems of products and services collectively with stakeholders' collaboration towards for efficient e-waste management.

Relevance to innovation. This paper presents an innovation of an e-waste management system, which is based on the product, services approach. The system encourages transition from selling electronics (which gives room to -pay as you throw- method, leading to informal e-waste management) to dematerialization which involves selling services rendered by electronics to satisfy consumer demands. Using this system, no e-waste is handled by consumers after the end of life of electronics therefore a reduced amount of the e-waste landing on landfills. The designer's role consisted of putting together customer's, provider's and policy makers into the design of the Product-Service Systems.

Key Words. Electrical and electronics equipments, end of Life, E-waste, product-service systems, system design.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, among all other streams of waste, e-waste has surfaced to be one of the hastily growing streams. The production of large quantities of e-waste has resulted due to the increased consumption of electronic products. This is an outcome of technological product obsolescence because of the global rapid economic development. Arguably, e-waste poses one of the greatest environmental challenges regionally as it is estimated that 3000 tons of e-waste from electronic devices are generated yearly in Kenya. This is directly linked to increased importation of sub-standard or poor quality equipment in the country despite deployment of the Basel and Bamako conventions that controls the trans-boundary movement of harmful wastes. Due to improper management system for e-waste, informal recycling procedures are still been used such as dumping

Figure 1: Product-Service System types (Tukker, 2004)

and open air burning regardless of the fact that Nairobi undertakes formal e-waste recycling practices. This possesses unpleasant effects on the people's health especially those living near these disposal areas not forgetting the environment. Due to these potential hazards, evaluation and establishment of efficient integrated e-waste management system was critical. Unfortunately, in Kenya, there is inefficient management system to address how to collect, transport, treat, safely dispose and monitor of electronics waste flows (Waema & Muriuki, 2008). Furthermore, due to unproductive waste management system, stakeholders do not take up their responsibilities in regard to e-waste disposal. This study endeavored to develop a product service system for e-waste management in Nairobi County.

The objectives of this study were:

- To determine the influence of existing systems of e-waste management on management of electronic waste in Nairobi county.
- To identify the sustainability priorities for the current e-waste management system in Nairobi County.
- To develop a service oriented system for e-waste management in Nairobi County.

According to ABED,(2006) in regard to customers preferences, e-waste Product-Service System signifies a transformed system enticing purchasing services and system solutions rather than purchasing products, which is likely to reduce the consumer needs and wants ecological impacts. These systems imply a top level of accountability for producer and service providers. Product-Service Systems may at times involve transfers of owner's property rights for both consumers and producers. The principal objective of Product-Service Systems is to lessen ecological impacts posed by means of using electronic items. These systems also allow the achievement of sustainability by providing a variety of social and economical benefits for business propositions (Sousa & Miguel, 2015). According to Adrodegari et al. (2015) , Product-Service System can be defined into five configurations categories ; ownership and service oriented as shown in Figure 1.

In ownership-oriented type of Product-Service System, services act as add-on to the products, which are the major source sales returns. One can sell the services without a contract or agreement or they may use an approach of maintenance contracts. In service-oriented types of Product-Service System, the main source of returns is the services that are firmly connected to the product to be used, and a customer is not given the chance to own a product. The various manufacturers and distributors are able to provide product-service systems for electronics, which promote selling of use of electronics rather than selling the electronics themselves for consumer ownership. It is no longer the 'product' that is the result, but rather the solutions. This context requires designing products that meet engineering requirements while simultaneously providing greater value for the customers, considering the new ownership structure of a Product-Service System . Hence, developing a Product-Service System is not merely a matter of choosing the best technical

Figure 2: Swiss e-waste management system flows (Wath et al., 2010)

solution but is rather about finding the best combination of products and services to maximize stakeholders' and customers' value.

Switzerland is majorly known as the pioneer country to design and implement a product – oriented e-waste management scheme that is formal and well-organized entailing collection to disposal of e-waste materials (Wath et al., 2010). The Swiss system works under a recycling fee that based on products. To ensure that there is enough funds for running the system, an Advance Recycling Fee is gathered from all buyers as they purchase fresh electronics. This fee funds operations of the whole system, as the manufacturers incur the full implementation responsibility and operating e-waste from all brands in the Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre field (Widmer et al. 2005). In addition, the fee equals to the differences between entire system cost and sum of e-waste value recovered. In this system operation, there is no consumer responsibility, hence a reduced amount of waste that ends up in the landfills as shown in Figure 2.

METHODS

A case study based approach was adopted for this research whereby the researcher collected data at Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre which is located in Mihango, Embakasi, off the Eastern By-pass in Nairobi, Kenya. This center mainly recycles e-waste together with offering collection of e-waste services, dismantling and processing services that are automated in Nairobi and other numerous key Kenyan cities. Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre mainly gets e-waste from the public, private sector, and domestic sector using collection campaigns.

This study relied on mixed method design for data collection and for comprehensive data analysis. Strategy of enquiry was convergent parallel mixed methods where both qualitative and quantitative data were merged by the researcher so that the research problem is provided in a comprehensive analysis (Creswell, 2014). Quantitative data was obtained from numeric description from opinions, attitudes and trends of the key informants such as private consumers, Hewlett Packard and Waste Electrical And Electronic Equipment Centre on the use of a product-service system for e-waste management through structured questionnaires and interviews. Further, qualitative data was obtained from the case study in which the researcher developed an in-depth

analysis of a case using in depth unstructured interviews, observation and desktop study to provide comprehensive information. According to Waema & Muriuki (2008), the e-waste 'universe' in Kenya consists of stakeholders such as distributors, assemblers, retailers, consumers, refurbishes, recyclers and final waste disposers to policy-makers. Thus, the target population of this study was Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre (encompasses recyclers, refurbishers), Hewlett Packard a cooperate consumer and private consumers that bring their e-waste to Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre.

Purposive sampling was utilized to select key informants that included the managerial, recycling department, refurbishing and education department at Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre and Hewlett Packard who are crucial in explaining the e-waste phenomenon in Nairobi County. Simple random sampling was used to select respondents from private and corporate consumers who frequently deliver e-waste at Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre. For the convenience of data analysis and discussion the sample size for the study consisted of four respondents from the organizations' departments and one producer. From the organizations database, there were 30 frequent private and corporate consumers. Only 10 consumers were randomly selected hence, the total number of respondents was 15. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches were used for data collection. The instruments for data collection were first pre-tested (piloting) and readjusted to ensure accurate capturing of the required data.

Mainly, the study was qualitative involving utilizing interviews with the use of a set of confidential unstructured interview schedules for the key informants. This allowed much greater freedom to seek clarification, in case of need, allowed development of supplementary questions or omission of certain questions that might have been tackled or solved from the subject's reaction. The researcher conducted site visits at Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre, and Hewlett Packard distributors and carried out face-to-face interviews so as to better understand the existing situations together with assessing the quality of the work done as well as the processes used. All responses were written down for later analysis. Observation was done to inform or show type of e-waste delivered in Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre and how it was handled. As one of the core data collection methods, the study used observation to directly seek and obtain information from the subjects in the case study without necessarily seeking their responses. To collect and keep records of the observed data, the study used digital cameras to gather and store observed data for later examination. The secondary data was obtained from the previous documented information about National Environment Management Authority and Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment Centre in Kenya to get more information on how they handle their e-waste management in Nairobi County.

Data Analysis and Management

Quantitative Method - Data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics whereby all numerical information gathered in the field was analyzed using rankings, percentages, and frequencies. Data results were presented in tables and figures for interpretation.

Qualitative Method - All data collected using qualitative methods such as key informant interviews and questionnaires in this study was sorted and arranged into themes and descriptions which was represented in a qualitative narrative to convey the findings of the analysis. An interpretation of the data was done which aided in designing the product service system for e-waste management.

RESULTS

The interviews from case study departments and producer were answered together with those of the two corporate consumers collaborating with the case study. Out of the projected private

consumers 75% answered questionnaires. All informants agreed to having at least some end of life electronics in their houses whereby 20% claimed that they kept them as souvenirs, 60% did not know where to take it and 20% for future use. Respondents who would rent electronics but on condition that data protection was provided as it is cheaper to source were 60%. On the question about disposal, 80% of the informants agreed to have discarded their e-waste at one point through the pay as you throw mechanism to the solid waste collectors. All informants thought it would be important for National Environment Management Authority to ensure that e-waste is managed in the appropriate manner in the country.

From the case study which is NEMA licensed, one respondent pointed out that the organization gets e-waste such as medical equipments, household equipment and office equipments from several private and cooperate consumers at a fee. Unfortunately, it was reported that the capacity of the organization to deal with e-waste was 350 tons per year but only about, 200-250 tones are received annually. It was also reported that a number of consumers did not understand why they have to pay to have their e-waste recycled. Some public organizations and institutions do not to pay this fee according to the responses given. On the question on the type the e-waste processes the company undertakes a respondent reported the they dismantle, separate, shred, refurbish and export harmful materials for further recycling for ecological preservation. In the process raw materials, such as plastics and metals are recovered and sold to small companies for making items such as recycled plastic posts. In social sustainability questions, it was responded that the company train their workers for a period of one year, which gives the workers skills therefore improving their lives. From the refurbishing sector, the organization also donates electronics after data wiping and maintains electronics at a fee.

On a question about the key obstacles facing appropriate e-waste collection it was reported by one respondent that currently there is no legal framework in Kenya for e-waste management and also that the 2006 Act e-waste is not categorized alone but under hazardous waste. In addition, it was mentioned that there has been a proposed draft e-waste bill 2013 pending in parliament. It was also reported that management of e-waste was expensive therefore; no other formal companies have ventured into it. Besides these, many people lack awareness on e-waste management. Lastly, most of the original electronics and electrical equipment manufacturers were said to be irresponsible for their end of life products despite the existence of the extended producer responsibility. The respondent recommended that the government should enforce the producer responsibility for appropriate e-waste management. From the response therefore it is noted that a system or framework and policy should be developed to aid in managing e-waste. Additionally the pending e-waste bill should be passed into a law so that manufacturers can take responsibility of their e-waste seriously. Creating awareness to consumers about e-waste management is also seen also a major input in managing e-waste in the country. The distributor respondent reported that they had little quantities of e-waste collected from consumers since most consumers believe that they should be paid for bringing back their end of life products. On the question of whether they would rent products to consumers the respondents thought it would be a good idea as the demand would go high due to the low prices. The only concern was that some consumers might not bring back product after getting the services.

Desktop data on NEMA, which is a governmental representative whose main objective entails ensuring universal conformity and implementation of environment policies as well as making standards and laws to prosecute offenders who violate the prescribed provisions, showed that they proposed a 2013 Bill. In this bill, it is proposed that producers intending to bring in new or second-hand electrical and electronic equipment into Kenya will be required to apply for registration from the authority. In addition, every producer will only obtain an annual compliance certificate upon declaring the previous year's weight of electrical and electronic equipment introduced in the market by product type and production of a valid contractual agreement with a licensed treatment facility. Lastly, every producer shall ensure that e-waste returned under individual take-back schemes, is not disposed of at municipal disposal site/facility. Recyclers will be required to ensure

Figure 3: Product-service systems design process (Tischner & Vezzoli, 2009)

that e-waste is dismantled in a safe manner for the environment by establishing infrastructure that allows recycling that is environmentally friendly and technologies that are sound (NEMA, 2013). The bill also outlines that, refurbishers shall ensure that the resultant e-waste is transferred to a collection centre or to licensed recyclers and that every person involved in the repair or refurbishment of electrical and electronic equipment shall ensure that the e-waste is recycled in a facility licensed by the Authority (NEMA, 2013).

DISCUSSION

Methodological Concerns in Designing Product-service Systems

From the data collected from the case study and stakeholders, we propose a product -service system design as the best method to help solve the e-waste management challenge in the country. This system is based on a shift from selling electronics to provision of a unit of satisfaction to consumers, stakeholder collaboration, and access to services rather than ownership of electronics as shown in the figure 3. The Product-Service System design for e-waste management was based on the following approaches-: Stakeholder configuration approach, which mainly is based on the interaction of stakeholders in the system, satisfaction approach which is related to satisfying consumer demands in relation to products and services. Lastly, the sustainability approach which relates to economical, social and economical beneficial solutions.

Interaction of Stakeholders in the System

An field exploratory study by Schluep et al. (2008) indicated that the waste e-waste re-processing systems are typically based on existing collaborative network amongst the manufactures, traders, recyclers and consumers. Each key player in the scheme is tasked to provide value addition, job creation at every point of processing chain in which in turn is also the cascade of activities involved in the reuse, recycling and disposal of e-waste. Using the SDO Toolkit shown Figure 4, a concept-profiling map involving different stakeholders was developed.

From Figure 4, consumers are to rent large electronics from producers and pay for them for the use. The consumers are required to return the electronics to the manufacturers or distributors after use. For the existing electronics and small equipments the consumer will purchase them from consumers but with an additional advance recycling fee.

After the end of life of these products, the consumer will be required to take them freely to the manufacturers take back collection points similarly to the Switzerland e-waste collection system that mainly relies on extended producer responsibility. This fee will be used to finance the whole e-waste management process, which includes, collection, transport of e-waste, recycling and training. The informal sector participants can get employment from the different take back collection centres. The manufacturers and distributors will be responsible for taking this e-waste to recycling and refurbishing centres at a fee. Raw materials recovered from the system will be sold other to make new products.

Figure 4: Concept profiling Map using SDO toolkit (Source: Case study findings)

Satisfaction and Sustainable Approaches for Product-Service System for e-Waste Management

In this system manufacturers will offer large electronics to consumers on rental terms rather than selling them. This lessens the initial purchase fees, which was originally too high, therefore electronics can be accessed more easily by all consumers through selling the "unit of satisfaction" rather than the electronic. Simultaneously, it is anticipated that advertising the new services or adopting alternative products and substitute systems of product-service utilization can assist in new job creation. Additionally, employment opportunities may be created through labour-services such as information services on design, collection systems, take back systems, repair, refurbishment and disassembly offer support training and, process of installation repair, maintenance together with treatment of their End-of-life components. (Elia & Gnoni, 2015). On the other hand, consumers gain from a product-service system by obtaining a greater variety of options of electronics in the market; various payment schemes; repair services and the vision of diverse systems of electronic utilization which are suitable to them on basis of possession responsibilities. In that consumers are free from the responsibility of an electronic; this is absolutely under the ownership of the producer in its whole life span.

Through Product-Service System, buyers can learn more on ecological properties of electronics as well as how they can contribute to reduce the environmental effects arising from electronic consumption. Product-Service System's have the potential to reduce the sum of products by the introduction of substitutes of product use such as pooling, sharing or leasing to end-users, without affecting the product design. To compliment this offer, the manufacturers will be responsible for maintenance, repairing, upgrading their electronic components and the treatment of their end-of-life components thus reducing the unexpected small costs incurred by consumers. Through Product-Service System, manufacturers will become more accountable for their product and services lest material cycles are closed (Adrodegari et al., 2015). Manufactures are encouraged to retract their commodities, improve, renovate and put them for use. Eventually, less e-waste ends up in incineration or open landfills.

Product-Service System approach will transform the current economic pricing systems as cost of production will become smaller in reference to cost incurred while making a product accessible to the end-user. This implies that the end-user do not pay for the product rather for the service offered which in turn can be perceived as technical improvement of dematerialization (Corvellec & Stal, 2017).

In the end, the development of an appropriate Product-Service System with a well-organized take back scheme for the small and already existing e-waste with consumers will possibly entice

Figure 5: Proposed Product Service System for e-waste management (Source: Case study findings)

end-user to return their End-of-Life electronics as shown in Figure 5. Second it will ensure that electronics at disposal stage have a worth market value. In the third state of a cost-effective Product-Service System is to adopt a substitute scenario of product application to generate extra profit. For instance, the legislation can require that a producer of an electronic to take care of their electronics after they are sold out. Under such scenario, the maintenance of the product accrues an extra cost. In case the manufacturer, rather than selling the electronic, decides to offer its utility, it typically becomes a profit maker and a incentive to minimize the utilization of the electronic that is favorable for the consumer as well (Sousa & Miguel, 2015).

The Product-Service System to be in Figure 5 also recommends the use-oriented services approach, which may include Product leasing whereby the ownership of the product does not change. The ownerships rights are reserved for the producer, who often takes the responsible of maintaining, repairing and controlling the product. The end-user pays value charges mainly for product utilization and normally has limitless access to the leased product (Tukker, 2004). In addition Product renting can also be utilized whereby the producers generally owns the product and is also accountable for maintenance, repair and control of the product. The end-users are charged for making use of the item, however, the end-user has limited access to the product implying that different end-users can utilize the same product at other times (Tukker, 2004). Lastly, product pooling which is much similar to product renting, although it encompasses synchronized utilization of the product (Tukker, 2004).

In the system, the government can execute institutional frameworks and policies which can be put in place to deal with the management of e-waste challenge in the county. Therefore the product service system has been developed from the findings of the study and mainly relies on collaborative and consultative process with all e-waste stakeholders.

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